

Creating Positive Social Impact through Sports Events

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Abstract

This research intends to measure the degree of relationship between sports events and its positive social impact. To validate the context of this research, primary data has been used and a verified model has projected which carry variable of sports events, sports participation, social cohesion, social impact, and community development. This research was conducted over sample of 400 individuals. With the use of adequate software, several tests were conducted to deduce the findings of how sports events and sports participation can cause social cohesion and the social impact in community development.

Keywords: Sports Participation, Sports Events, Social Cohesion, Social Impact, Community Development.

Introduction

Our research “creating positive social impact through sports events” inspect on how sporting activities can have a beneficial social effect on society. This includes the influence of sporting events that people from different backgrounds, come under one roof. Sports exercises can add to improving the personal satisfaction, expanding pride, the feeling of having a place of residents, sporting freedoms, and can assist with empowering nearby investment. Several short term and long-term advantages have been claimed to support the hosting of substantial sports events. Whereas the economic impact of sports events has been the center focus that has received most of the consideration.

The study briefs the significance and establishment of the perceived social impact of sports events by anatomize the data acquire from local attendees of the 2012 FedEx st. Jude Classic. The result proves that social impact is created in sports events if the attendees feel a greater sense of companionship at the event or discern a higher level of the social responsibility at the event. Researchers have now gradually shifted from inaugurating economic impact to measuring the social impact of the sports events (Walton et al., 2008). In the 2012 Olympics in London the intangible benefits were found more predominant and highlighted by the citizens across the country, as compared to the intangible benefits such as Economic gains and improved infrastructure (Mourato et al. 2005).

Today, all sports events either at a smaller or larger scale is considered as significant mechanism for social and economic development. Government and other public and sports authorities are pursuing to boost their ability to pull off social and economic objectives by investigating in sports events (Kellet et al., 2008; Misener, 2015; Cornelissen, 2008)

As interests in sport events have increased sport occasions have gotten the subject of public examination. Requests for 'proof' supporting the assertion of sports events coordinators that they add to the public great have begun to amass (Hover et al., 2016). Studies have found that till date the main impact of sports events have been economic in nature, while through the considerations of the social impact are comparatively scarce (Preuss, 2004).

Many studies have been investigating the non-cognitive social impact incorporated with sporting events, it is generally surmised that social impact can include both positive and negative elements of sports events. Social exchange theory has been widely used as a base to understand and examine citizens thoughts of social impact based on awareness, attitude, and intention (ap, 1992; Jurowksi et al., 1997). The communities that want to

inrush from the benefit of sport events have been investing and growing in numbers in terms of hosting frequency (sato et al., 2014). Disregarding of size of the event, they are recognized internationally as an important aspect of tourism (Getz, 1997; Gammon & Robinson, 2003; Penot, 2003; Sofield, 2003; Zauhar, 2004).

Therefore, the objective of this study is to elaborate the perspectives of two community development theories and join them with potential community development goals. This way will allow the citizens to be supportive of sports community.

Problem Statement

Our research topic is “Creating a positive social impact through sport events”. Now even though there have been researches that have been conducted regarding the relationship between social impact and sports events there hasn’t been research conducted that specifically talks about positive social change being created by such events. Community development goals identify problem areas (e.g., lack of venues or trained people) and see how the sport event hosting can boost these community development goals. The research has shown the intangible impact like economic development through the sports events. Our goal is to create tangible social impact, which helps in growth if an individual, country, and state. There may have been research conducted regarding social impact created due to other activities such as tourism but not sport events. Therefore, it was important to conduct this research as sport events is slowly and gradually returning to Pakistan with the emergence of the PSL and the improving law and order situation of the country. We could see some of the impacts and legacies that could be set as long- term goals for our community.

Research Questions

The research questions for this study are as follows

1. Does sports participation play an impact on social cohesion?
2. Does sports event put an impact on community development?

Significance of the Study

The study is beneficial for the sports event organizers as well as the government to make progressing strategies in the future. The sports organizers can take help to increase the harmony between the different communities to create a positive social impact. The study will help the government to create more and more sports opportunities for the people and create a positive social impact that may benefit the country in different ways.

Research Objectives

Research objective is basically the basis of a particular research.

This research was conducted to study if sports events create any kind of a positive social impact on the society or on individuals. For any research to be conducted it is important to consider the dependent and independent variables. There are two independent variables and three dependent variables in this research. The independent variables of this research are `sports events` and `sports participation`, whereas the dependent variables of this research are `social cohesion`, social impact` and `community development.

This research will lead us to understand if sports events have a direct positive impact on social outcomes. It will explain if increased sports participations bring social cohesion in return bringing positive social outcomes and will help to understand the effect of sports events and social impacts on positive community development.

Literature Review

Background on Social Impact

Social Impact theory defines social influence in terms of fields of social force that affect us, forcing us to think or act in a specific way. The physical forces that control the propagation of light, sound, gravity, magnetism, etc., have been equated with these social forces. The amount of light that falls on a tabletop, for instance, is a result of the intensity of the lights reflecting on the table, their distance from the table, and the number of lights

present. The social impact felt by a person should be a function of the power, immediacy, and number of individuals who are present in an analogous way. Thus, the social force felt by a target person should all directly influence these three components, or definitions, of source individuals (Latané, 1981; Latané & Nida, 1980)

Social Impact solely shows us the benefits of such events that have an internal focus on the local population (Crompton, 2004). It is a fact that sports tourism events held at a mass scale can grab a lot of attention, such as the FIFA World Cup, around the world (Kim & Walker, 2012). These sporting events are “hallmark” events due to which both positive and negative impacts occur in the country hosting these events (Ritchie & Aitken, 1985; Ritchie, 1984). There has been a lot of attention that has been shifted towards the social impact that sports events can create (Baldock, Maes, & Buelens, 2011; Chalip, 2006; Crompton, 2004; Kim & Walker, 2012; Waite, 2003). The “Social Exchange Theory” refers to the idea of the interaction of two interdependent variables, where the action of one variable impacts the other (Blau, 1964; Emerson, 1976).

Sporting Events and its Impact on Community Development

According to the findings of research done on tourism, suggest that people’s positive interpretation of the impact created by tourism would create a positive inclination towards development in that regard which is prevalent in the social exchange theory as the reciprocal effect (Andereck et al., 2005; Ap, 1992; Fredline, 2004). The reliability and accuracy of the research is a bit questionable as the questionnaires were constructed using existing research which may not cover the entirety of the topic as well the mixed notions and perceptions of the respondents (Kim et al., 2015; Inoue & Havard, 2014).

There have been various studies conducted on the role of sporting events on the social impacts that it has on the community and amongst the population living in the sporting events but one of the most significant contributions to this area of research was given in the study by Taks, et al, (2015) in which the scholars determined the impact of sporting events for the local communities of the area. In the study, he explored the various impacts that sporting events have on the community like the more obvious economic impacts as well as the boost in tourism of the area during those sports events but also the less obvious impacts like the social benefits that the community receives because of those events. According to the study by Heere, et al, (2013), the 2010 World Cup that was held in South Africa enhanced social unity within the area as it led to the feelings of euphoria, unity as well as an increase in national pride for the community which was observed by the findings of the results of the study.

However, these positive social impacts that are caused because of the sporting events within the area are always desired by the organizers, but they are not often the main objective for hosting the sporting events in the area as per the study by Smith (2009). The above point was contrasted in the study by Taks (2013) which compared the observed social impacts as well as the outcomes of the bigger sport events and the local sporting events too by using several perspectives like the human capital, power relations, socialization as well as urban regeneration. The outcomes from the study showed that the local sporting events or the events that were held on a smaller scale yielded more beneficial outcomes for the local communities in terms of the social benefits as compared to the mega sporting events. This finding was since these events held on a local scale allowed for more opportunities for the community to strengthen their social network and the connections between the communities due to the event (Taks, 2013).

Moreover, another study that contributed greatly to the literature already present was by Pranić, et al, (2012) which was conducted to investigate the perceptions of the local community of the area after the World Men’s Handball Championship had been hosted in 2009 in Split which is a Croatian city. The study was conducted with a quantitative method which included the convenience sampling method used on the primary data collected in the form of surveys of 92 participants. These surveys were tested by the Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests to check for the social impacts of the events among the several outcomes. The findings from the study showed that the perceptions of the respondents were positive mostly and there were positive social impacts within the local community as a result of the social events, but the findings of the study also showed that a small percentage of the respondents would have liked the finances from the public spending to be used for facilities

that were much needed like healthcare centers as well as educational purposes instead of for one-time events. This study is significant as it is one of the few pieces of literature that tries to accurately measure the level of social impact that these sporting events cause and it also includes the social exchange theory in its research and obtains its findings of the social impacts by first validating them with the social impacts scale (Pranić, et al, 2012).

Furthermore, another study was conducted, to empirically investigate the social impacts of the major sporting events on the local community that is hosting them, by Liu (2016). This study was based in Shanghai and the methodology used for the study was primary data that was in the form of questionnaires from which they received 450 valid completed questionnaires for the sample size of the research. The findings from the research conducted showed that out of the six impacts that were tested in the questionnaires, four of them tested positive and the negative impacts included the inconvenience caused to the residents because of the sporting event as well as the environmental pollution caused within the area. Overall, the social impacts of the sporting events were observed to be positive for the host community. This research paper was significant in the literature present on the social impact of sports events as it showed the overall perception that most communities are going to have towards the sporting events being hosted in the community, but it showed the need for the event portfolio approach to be taken in further research to accurately measure the social impact of sports events on the host community (Liu 2016).

Social Cohesion and Link to Sporting Events

Social Cohesion has been described as the shared connections and the values between the different members of the community and the sense of solidarity among them. It makes them aware that they are surrounded by various members within the same community and face similar shared challenges that the community faces (Schiefer & Van Der Noll, 2017). One way that was derived to measure the social cohesion was to measure the social capital that the community has which is described as the shared resources and information amongst the community. According to the study by Fonseca et al. (2019) social cohesion is considered as an important feature of a resilient city and various initiatives are taken to help the communities develop social cohesion to face the challenges that the society faces.

Sporting events are one such initiative taken by the community to promote growth for the community within the area whether that growth is in terms of economic growth or in terms of healthier lifestyles and increased amounts of social cohesion within the population in the area (Sherry, et al, 2015). Having sports events within the area allows the diverse population of the community to gather in the sport and physical activity programs of the local events and it also allows for the members of diverse cultural, ethnic, social as well as geographical communities. Hence these sports events provide the community with the chance to develop and increase the social capital.

In the study by Bruening et al. (2015) which is based on the concept of managing sports events and organizing them to manage social change within the community. The purpose of the study is to determine the impact of participating in these sporting events as volunteers which are organized and managed for the development of the community. The methodology used for conducting the study was a mixed method approach to determine the social capital that was developed of the community after a sport learning event had been organized for the alumni with the goal for developing the social capital. The findings obtained from the study showed the practical results obtained from organizing and managing the sports events to promote and develop the social capital of the community and increase the social cohesion of the members in the area as well as allowing them to build their networks and connections further.

Moreover, another source that significantly contributed to the literature present on social cohesion achieved through sport events was the study by Schulenkorf, and Edwards (2012) which was carried out to investigate the sporting events that were organized for the sole purpose of development of the community socially in terms of the social capital as well as the social cohesion and unity of the community. The findings from the study showed significant results of the sporting events and there was development observed in the social capital of the members of the community after the sports event had been hosted. The significance of the results of the study

showed that sports events organized for the social development of the community is an effective measure to increase the social interactions of the members of the community through these various sports as well as ancillary event opportunities to build the social cohesion of the community and increase the networks and connections of the various members of the community.

Organizing sports events within the local community divides to several direct as well as indirect impact for the community which include economic impacts, physical, political as well as social impacts among various others. Much of the planning behind organizing and managing sports events within the community are done due to the economic and political impact on the community but these events also significantly impact the social as well as cultural environment of the community. According to the study by Nicholson and Hoye (2008) which was done for the purpose of investigating the relationship between sports events and the social capital, the findings from the study show that having sports events within the community leads to the development of social capital as well as increasing the connections of the community and the promotion of the social justice and well-being of the members of the community. Participation at these sports events provides the members of the community with multiple opportunities to socialize together with the other members and develop connections with them and increase the social cohesion of the community as well as increasing communication between them and the sense of unity too (Schulenkorf & Edwards, 2012).

Sports Participation Effect on Social Impact

Jeroen Vermeulen and Paul Verweel argued that participation in sports will allow individuals to develop skills in the social inclusion and exclusion processes, often subtle and situational. The general benefits of sporting activities and spectatorship can include: (1) improving health and exercising the excess energy of students; (2) compliance with competition or community laws and restricting delinquent activities (such as stealing, behaving aggressively, consuming illegal drugs, and drinking excessive alcohol, etc.); (3) fostering social standards, honesty and building character; (4) improving confidence, encouragement, empowerment and self-esteem; (5) providing social engagement, fun and enjoyment; (6) providing opportunities for sports education and career; (7) expanding life experience and making more friends; (8) learning how to cope with disappointment and challenging circumstances; and (9) developing life skills (Blinde, Taub, & Han, 1993; Coakley, 2007; Eitzen & Sage, 2008; Hudson, 2000; OPERD, 2004; Shaffer & Wittes, 2006; Woods, 2006; Woodruff & Schallert, 2008). Participation in sporting activities is positively related to casual socialization and encourages partnerships (Becker & Haring, 2012; Perks, 2007; Ulseth, 2004). Participation in sports groups is important for friendship and peer relationships (Felfe, Lechner, & Steinmayr, 2016; Gerlach & Brettschneider, 2013; Pawlowski et al., 2016).

In terms of political commitment, Delaney and Kearny (2005) and Seippel (2006) consider a strong relation between sport and social involvement. However, studies mentioned in this article use cross-sectional data and do not take problems originating between sports participation and social capital formation into consideration (Becker & Haring, 2012; Delaney & Kearny, 2005; Gerlach & Brettschneider, 2013; Perks, 2007; Seippel, 2006; Ulseth, 2004).

Sports Events Effect on Social Cohesion

Sports events can have a positive social impact as Shone et al (2013) suggested that because of the consequence of the atmosphere being created, major sporting events have a positive impact on social interaction. The arguments of the politicians suggested that mega sporting events build social solidarity and bind the nation together as South African President Zuma has publicly claimed (Bell, 2010). Major sports events such as The Rugby World Cup 2015 can significantly enhance social cohesion and local community if the event is organized and executed rightly. Participation of people in inter-community sporting activities may serve as the initial point for the development of community networks and bonds that are essential for social cohesion (Misener & Mason, 2006). Sport can serve as 'sociological superglue,' it is argued, linking people together through pride and shared goal (Tonts, 2005; Putnam, 2000).

Social cohesion acting as a mediator has both its impact on sports events and social impact. Social cohesion is the continuous process of creating a culture of common values, shared problems, and equal opportunities, centered on a sense of faith, trust, hope, and mutuality (Jenson, 1998), because of sporting events. By creating social capital, sport will contribute to community growth and civil regeneration (Delaney & Keaney, 2005). This principle extends from the supposed beneficial characteristics of sport, such as improved contact, teamwork, tolerance, respect, cohesion, etc. (Svoboda, 1994). Historically, the suggestion that sport can help develop a sense of community' has been crucial to the legitimization of the provision of public leisure (Glyptis, 1989), and it is also believed that sport can bring people together across cultural, ethnic and class divisions (European Commission, 2007).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework:

- H1: There is a positive significant relationship between Sport Participation and Social Cohesion.*
- H2: There is a positive significant relationship between Sports Event and Social Cohesion.*
- H3: There is a positive significant relationship between Social Cohesion and Social Impact.*
- H4: There is a positive significant relationship between Social Cohesion and Community Development.*
- H5: There is a positive significant relationship between Social Impact and Community Development.*

Sport Participation and Social Cohesion

Participation of people in inter-community sporting activities may serve as the initial point for the development of community networks and bonds that are essential for social cohesion (Misener & Mason, 2006).

Participation in sporting activities is positively related to casual socialization and encourages partnerships (Becker & Haring, 2012; Perks, 2007; Ulseth, 2004). Participation in sports groups is important for friendship and peer relationships (Felfe, Lechner, and Steinmayr, 2016; Gerlach & Brettschneider, 2013; Pawlowski et al., 2016).

The general benefits of sporting activities and spectatorship can include: abiding by the community laws and restricting delinquent activities (such as stealing, behaving aggressively, doing drugs) ; fostering social standards, honesty and building character; improving confidence, encouragement, empowerment and self-esteem; providing social engagement, fun and enjoyment; providing opportunities for sports education and career; expanding life experience and making more friends; learning how to cope with disappointment and challenging circumstances; and developing skills of life (Blinde, Taub, & Han, 1993; Coakley, 2007; Eitzen & Sage, 2008; Hudson, 2000; OPERD, 2004; Shaffer, & Wittes, 2006; Woods, 2006; Woodruff & Schallert, 2008). Therefore, based on the above argument on the relationship between Sports Participation and Social Cohesion, we can propose the following hypothesis.

H1: There is a positive significant relationship between Sport Participation and Social Cohesion.

Sports Event and Social Cohesion:

The arguments of the politicians suggested that mega sporting events build social solidarity and bind the nation together as South African President Zuma has publicly claimed (Bell,2010). Major sports events such as The Rugby World Cup 2015 can significantly enhance social cohesion and local community if the event is organized and executed rightly. Sport can serve as 'sociological superglue,' it is argued, linking people together through pride and shared goal (Tonts, 2005; Putnam, 2000).

By creating social capital, sport will contribute to community growth and civil regeneration (Delaney & Keaney, 2005). Social cohesion is a process in which community shared values are developed, challenges are shared, and equal chances are given, based upon trust, hope, and reciprocity (Jenson, 1998).

Therefore, on the basis of the above argument on the relationship between Sports Event and Social Cohesion, we can propose the following hypothesis.

H2: There is a positive significant relationship between Sports Event and Social Cohesion.

Social Cohesion and Social Impact:

Social cohesion is the continuous process of creating a culture of common values, shared problems, and equal opportunities, centered on a sense of faith, trust, hope, and mutuality (Jenson, 1998), because of sporting events. Historically, the suggestion that sport can help develop a sense of community' has been crucial to the legitimization of the provision of public leisure (Glyptis, 1989), and it is also believed that sport can bring people together across cultural, ethnic and class divisions (European Commission, 2007).

This principle extends from the supposed beneficial characteristics of sport, such as improved contact, teamwork, tolerance, respect, cohesion, etc. (Svoboda, 1994). According to a study focused on social impact stated that social impact can refer back to the mode in which sport event prompts changes in collective and somebody, value systems, behavior patterns, culture, social structure, lifespan style, and life quality (Taks, 2013).

Therefore, based on the above argument on the relationship between Social Cohesion and Social Impact, we can propose the following hypothesis.

H3: There is a positive significant relationship between Social Cohesion and Social Impact.

Social Cohesion and Community Development

Community development is a process where people come together to take action on what's important to them. Community development has been characterized by a wide range of courses in the writing (Christenson, Fendley, & Robinson, 1989; Hutchison & Nogradi, 1996; United Nations, 1955). Vail (1992, 1993) contended for a community development way to deal with improved correspondence furthermore, joint effort among network accomplices associated with the sport event locally.

Hutchison and Nogradi (1996) and Pedlar (1996) have recognized the importance of process, there is very little empirical work that shows how community development is shaped by process. It has been contended somewhere else that sporting events may fill in as a method for creating social capital (Misener & Mason, 2006) and add to community development (Hiller, 2000).This political philosophy has brought a market-arranged way to deal with the community development, like numerous urban areas around the globe endeavoring to utilize sport for advancement (Whitson & Horne, 2006).

Therefore, based on the above argument on the relationship between Social Cohesion and Community Development, we can propose the following hypothesis.

H4: There is a positive significant relationship between Social Cohesion and Community Development.

Social Impact and Community Development:

Countries from all around the world invest money in sport events intending to promote feelings such as self-belonging to a community or nation. It is also considered that the sense of belonging plays a positive role e.g.,

(Pawlowski et al., 2014). Kavetsos and Szymanski (2008) cited in (Cornelissen & Maennig, 2010) after thorough research figured out that conducting Olympics, the football world cup or the European football Championship played a major role in the happiness of European countries for almost three decades. Also, they figured out that a special effect takes place by World Cups which is not present at times of other events.

Pedlar (1996) calls attention to that network advancement is about a change cycle that may be encouraged by others yet is self-decided by the network. Notwithstanding, when attempting to discover experimental proof that sport events have added to intergroup fellowship and general community development, it gets evident that significantly more subjective and quantitative research is expected to either affirm or dismiss this case (Chalip, 2006; Coalter, 2007; Kidd, 2008).

Therefore, based on the above argument on the relationship between Social Impact and Community Development, we can propose the following hypothesis.

H5: There is a positive significant relationship between Social Impact and Community Development.

Methodology

Data Collection

The data has been collected of people who have played or haven't played part in participating in a sports event. This was done for the soul purpose of gathering perceptions and opinions about their understanding about the term sport and its effects. The data has been collected through online questionnaire survey to get better reach. The respondents of this survey were individuals ranging between the age barrier of 18 and above with no filters of background of education and learning. It also did not entertain any sorts of gender bias. To understand their point of view we used Likert scale for the responses.

Sampling Method

The sampling method or technique, which was used for our research, is nonprobability sampling technique following convenience sampling. We chose this technique because of time constrains, cost concerns and the ongoing global pandemic.

Sample Size

The sample size plays a vital role in research larger the sample size proportional to better the research. A sample size is the desired part of the whole population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). This research has a wide population across the field with no limits in the geographic and demographic condition of the country. Since there is Approx 21 million total population our sample size would be a minimum of 400 individuals in order to represent and support the research. The platform used for data collection was university students and social sites which accommodated us in gathering data from the city of Karachi. The questionnaire used a five point Likert scale for the research.

Data Collection Tools

For our data collection tools we used modern means of information input techniques for that purpose using internet as a platform we got our questionnaires filled which helped us analyze the data and break it down for statistical purposes.

Research Philosophy

The advancement of empiricism is positivism, which in most cases is associated with quantitative research (Ryan, 2018). There are two types of foundationalism philosophies from which empiricism stems according to which the researcher's own bias should not affect the research itself (Phillips & Burbules 2000). There are four major attributes of positivism which include "Phenomenalism", "Deductivism", "Objectivity" and "Inductivism" (Bryman, 2008). According to epistemology, a positivist belief is such that the researcher and the world are two separate entities, and that the world exists without the researchers' presence (Bryman, 2008, Howell, 2013). According to ontology, there is an outer reality that exists and through research and hypothesis, we can discover it, essentially by going backward and looking at the root cause of it (Howell, 2013).

Research Design

To create a causal relationship quantitative research must be conducted (Light, Singer, & Willett 1990). This is the stance of both positivists and empiricists which they have derived from David Hume's theory of causality (Baert, 1998:176–9). According to Hempel and Oppenheim (1948), the scientific reasoning of the occurrence of occasions comes from the primary situations and the common policies of commanding associations between fitting variables. The most influential causal conjecture in quantitative research is the regularity theory particularly in social sciences (Mohr, 1996).

Research Approach

Our research is based on a deductive approach. A deductive approach is research that is done by developing a hypothesis by studying existing theory. And then a research design is formed to find out whether our hypothesis is right or wrong. This research aims to find an effect on social impacts by sports events, sports participation, social cohesion, and community development. This research studies the impact of independent variables on dependent variables and then this is carried by positivist philosophy by deductive approach. The main dissimilarity between deductive and inductive research is that inductive research is about forming the theory whereas deductive research is about studying the theory.

Deductive approach:

- It's based on studying social phenomena.
- It starts by generating a hypothesis.
- A theory is developed to study why it happened.
- The theory is tested by research and the theory is either rejected or accepted.

Inductive approach:

- Data is collected on the possible reason why such a thing happened.
- Theory is formed.
- Develop a general conclusion.

Results

The tests conducted below are to check the acceptably, reliability and practicality of data set and hypothesis. These tests would determine whether the conducted research is acceptable or not.

Table 1

Reliability Statistics:

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Value
Sports Participation	.891
Sports Events	.710
Social Cohesion	.874
Social Impact	.916
Community Development	.865

The reliability statistics are conducted in order to check the reliability of the data. The Cronbach's Alpha values are used to see the reliability of social cohesion, social impact and community development in regard to sports events and sports participation. The values shown are above the value of acceptance (0.7) therefore it can be concluded that the variables are statistically reliable.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Sports Participation Mean	2.29	1.327	.803	-.645
Sports Events Mean	2.49	1.200	.546	-.671
Social Cohesion Mean	2.35	1.253	.824	-.568
Social Impact Mean	2.58	1.239	.615	-.840
Community Development Mean	2.72	1.123	.324	-.769

The descriptive statistics are done to check the normality of the data and by the conducted tests we can conclude that since the skewness and kurtosis of the data set is near to the value 0 therefore it can be concluded that the data set is normal. The standard deviation of the data set is also near to 1 therefore it is also correct. However, the mean should be greater than 2.5 for the variable to be accepted, but it can be seen that SP_M, SE_M and SC_M are below 2.5 so therefore the chances of rejection are more.

Table 3
Correlation

	Sports Participation	Sports Events	Social Cohesion	Social Impact	Community Development
Sports Participation	1				
Sports Events	.830	1			
Social Cohesion	.886	.875	1		
Social Impact	.874	.844	.890	1	
Community Development	.811	.811	.839	.901	1

Correlation test is also known as the discriminant test, this is used to explain us the similarity or how closely variables are correlated to each other. From the given test results we can see that there is a strong correlation between the variables.

Table 4
Social Cohesion

Model	Beta	t	Sig
Constant		1.659	.098
Sports Participation	.581	16.163	<.001
Sports Event	.376	10.454	<.001

The coefficient test is conducted to show relationship and significance of independent variables with dependent variables. The “P” value the significance should be less than 0.05 in order for the hypothesis to be acceptable. With the rule for “t” value stated that it should be “<2” for the relation to be acceptable. In this case we can see that social cohesion is an acceptable factor and approves the hypothesis and relation of independent variables with dependent variables.

Table 5
Model Summary

Model	R Square
1	.841

The R Square test determines the variance between dependent and independent variables and in this case, we can see that the two independent variables have 84% variance with respect to social cohesion which is a very positive sight.

Table 6
Social Impact

Model	Beta	t	Sig
Constant		6.160	<.001
Sports Participation	.553	13.878	<.001
Sports Event	.385	9.643	<.001

The coefficient test is conducted to show relationship and significance of independent variables with dependent variables. The “P” value the significance should be less than 0.05 for the hypothesis to be acceptable. With the rule for “t” value stated that it should be “<2” for the relation to be acceptable. In this case we can see that social impact is an acceptable factor and approves the hypothesis and relation of independent variables with dependent variables.

Table 7
Model Summary

Model	R Square
1	.808

The R Square test determines the variance between dependent and independent variables and in this case, we can see that the two independent variables have 80% variance with respect to social impact which is a very positive sight.

Table 8
Community Development

Model	Beta	T	Sig
Constant		11.707	<.001
Sports Participation	.446	9.348	<.001
Sports Event	.441	9.240	<.001

The coefficient test is conducted in order to show relationship and significance of independent variables with dependent variables. The “P” value the significance should be less than 0.05 for the hypothesis to be acceptable. With the rule for “t” value stated that it should be “<2” for the relation to be acceptable. In this case we can see that community development is an acceptable factor and approves the hypothesis and relation of independent variables with dependent variables.

Table 9
Model Summary

Model	R Square
1	.720

The R Square test determines the variance between dependent and independent variables and in this case, we can see that the two independent variables have 72% variance with respect to community development which is a very positive sight. Thus, from the tests we can conclude that all of the hypothesis are being accepted and are valid.

Conclusion

Findings of the study and test results have identified that there was a positive significant influence of sport participation on social cohesion and that sports events also have a significant effect on social cohesion therefore there is a positive impact on the concept of unity because of sports in general. On the other hand, it is shown that social cohesion also proves to be positive regarding the social impact and community building. However, it is not one of the independent variables but rather it is a dependent variable in the case and by that we can see that sports participation and sports events have a positive social impact and helps in community building as whole. So, we can conclude by implying that this research made an additional influence on the already existing work and research done on the topic of sports events and social impact. The hypotheses were accepted, and it suggests that the independent variables truly have an impact on the development of a community. It also recommends that with more opportunities the growth of the society and unity amongst the audience would increase with time and not only will that it helps with sustainability of the country but indirect promote and improve a lot of economic factors.

Limitations

The findings of this research have several limitations. A large set of audience could not be the part of this research. There were geographical constrains and ongoing pandemic conditions which limit the scope of this study. Underdeveloped countries cannot rely on sports to community development there can be other factors to. Since the data was collected online it is not sure that the respondents would have given their preferable views.

Future Research

This research can assist many other papers in the future by removing the limitations. Creation of awareness among people about the subject would ensure that people have correct responses. This would lead to much credible research results in return. Removing the geographical restrain, this research can support similar research papers that are done on a global scale with a much bigger audience. For future research, qualitative research approach could be used. Qualitative data obtained from in-depth focus group interviews is more likely to produce accurate outcomes, since there is a likelihood of high engagement of people followed by a lack of biasness on the part of consumers while answering the research questions. Further research work is encouraged and can produce even more ethical upbringings about the topic.

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